

Enabling demand response for optimal deployment of multi-carrier microgrids incorporating incentives

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Abstract

This paper inspects customer multi-carrier microgrid deployments' techno-economic viability and assists investors in deciding whether or not to invest in multi-carrier microgrid installations equipped with smart demand-side technologies. The solution of the proposed model determines the optimal mix and size of distributed energy resources, and identifies the ideal participation rate of potential responsive customers within the multi-carrier microgrid. The objective of the proposed model is to minimize the overall deployment cost comprising the investment and replacement of distributed energy resources, demand-side smart measurement and informing appliances, loan payoff, operation, maintenance, peak demand charge, energy demand shifting reward or penalty, emission, and unserved energy while ensuring the desired levels of reliability and online reserve. The model also considers incentive policies to encourage customers to install demand-side smart technologies to participate in demand response programs actively. The planning problem is formulated by mixed-integer programming. The proposed model is applied to an industrial zone as an aggregate load. Numerical simulations exhibit the model's efficacy and scrutinize in-depth, the effect of a variety of factors on multi-carrier microgrid planning results, including the extents of the capital investment fund and loan in addition to demand response enabling technology cost.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Microgrids (MGs) as key players in smart grids, comprised of distributed energy resources (DERs) and elastic loads, have attracted significant attention in recent years due to providing reliable and cost-effective energy solutions for energy consumers [1–3]. Although the advent of smart grid technologies such as 5G networks and 5G-based Internet of Things has propelled the integration of demand response programs (DRPs) [4], the impact of demand-side smart appliances' cost on enabling the potential responsive users as a promising tool in smart grids' territories has been dismissed. Thus, convincing MG business cases are required to justify the intense investment in DERs and demand response (DR) automation tools.

Numerous studies have been conducted on MG design. Ref. [5] proposes a model to optimally size and site photovoltaic

(PV) and battery units in an isolated community MG. The model further analyses the impact of installed units on power quality improvement and system loss. Ref. [6] designates an efficient stochastic planning model for standalone ac/dc MGs. The objective is to minimize the costs comprising the DERs investment, operation, and electronic converters. The economic analysis of a standalone multi-carrier microgrid (MCMG) is examined regarding battery degradation and reliability considerations [7]. The model highlights the indispensable use of dump load to prevent battery overcharging. Owing to the high initial investment cost of DERs, a regulated third-party-based MG planning is explored to alleviate economic barriers in the proliferation of prosumers by appealing to stakeholders to invest in remote and urban community energy systems [8]. A planning tool is developed to give guidelines for industrial MGs deployment by several stakeholders [9]. The model

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employs a game-theoretical framework that allows different and potentially conflicting objectives of stakeholders. A multi-agent system running by several stakeholders is developed to pave the way for the modelling of cooperative self-sustainable MCMGs [10]. The stakeholders entail the design agent, control agent, generation agent, load agent, and charging/refilling station agent. The paper in [11] presents an innovative bi-level model for the risk-based optimal design of MGs under uncertainties in demand and renewable generation. The model determines the optimal site and size of DERs together with partitioning the grid into several MGs. Ref. [12] develops a planning framework to design multi-energy systems to improve economic and environmental performance. A co-optimization scheme is presented to aid the community MG deployments in satisfying the requirements of U.S. Department of Energy and state renewable energy mandates [13]. Besides, the impact of regulatory constraints is studied for MG economic sustainability. Ref. [14] proposes a multi-period joint planning approach to determine the mix, size, and installation time of diverse DERs. The proposed framework considers the short- and long-term uncertainties of renewable generations, demands, and declining trend of battery investment cost. Empirical MCMG planning incorporating carbon-emission cut targets is developed to prepare a general guideline for expanding low-carbon districts with high penetration of renewable energy resources (RERs) [15]. A framework is presented to deploy low-carbon multi-energy districts by incentivizing renewable investment [16]. Ref. [17] presents a scenario-based planning model that provides an efficient solution for realizing low-cost and low-carbon MCMGs. An uncertainty matrix is employed as well to tackle renewable generations and multi-energy demands uncertainties. The work in [18] assesses the techno-economic and environmental sustainability of an MG that electrifies a residential community. Herein, the energy consumption of the community is predicted using an artificial neural network. An integrated planning model is developed to optimally size RERs and allocate the production schedule of a flow shop system [19]. The model aims to minimize the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) as well as to achieve environmental sustainability based on hourly climate analytics. An islanded hybrid MG's optimal sizing is conducted considering technical, economic, and environmental aspects [20]. The optimal sizing of a hybrid MG is studied considering technical, ecological and economic aspects [21]. A cost-effective optimization approach for optimal planning of an MG equipped with compressed air energy storage system is proposed [22].

According to the DR strategic plan of the International Energy Agency [23], "the demand-side activities should be active elements and the first choice in all energy policy decisions to create more reliable and more sustainable energy systems." A comprehensive survey on DR potentials and benefits in smart grids is presented [24]. An economic and technical solution for rural electrification of a village is provided by the optimal sizing of RERs [25]. It is declared that the LCOE of the MG reduces by using the demand shifting strategy of non-essential loads and RER penetrations. The objective of the model is to improve both the economic and reliability performances

considering time-of-use DRP. A methodology for optimal sizing of an MG is presented, accounting for the lifetime of battery and generator units based on the usage [26]. The model incorporates electric vehicles and pumped water storage as dynamic loads to participate in DRPs. A two-stage stochastic planning framework is proposed to optimally allocate battery and micro-turbine assets within an MG [27]. Hot water systems and interruptible loads are considered as controllable loads to smooth renewable fluctuations in the model. The optimal stochastic planning of a distributed hydrogen-based multi-energy system is presented to address RER uncertainties and improve the system's energy efficiency [28]. A hydrogen-water-based storage system is introduced to enhance the flexibility of the system for DR purposes. The optimal planning of a multi-energy system considering the inevitable uncertainties of electrical, heating, and cooling demands, as well as the wind turbine (WT) generation, is acquired using a decomposing approach [29]. Moreover, the model employs the demand shifting strategy and explores its impact on planning solutions. Ref. [30] proposes a probabilistic dynamic planning procedure for residential energy systems to minimize customer costs. Controllable electrical and thermal appliances are employed in the model to tackle PV oscillations. An extended work of the prior publication is proposed in [31], which considers the possible PV energy curtailment cost. The results declare that PV curtailment consideration in the objective function has a significant impact on PV penetration within residential communities. The paper in [32] determines the long-term configuration and sizing of a multi-energy system incorporating an integrated DRP. This work employs various DR strategies, including transferable, shiftable, and curtailable approaches applied to cooling, heating, and electrical demands to improve the system's investment economy and operational flexibility.

A preference-based DR multi-objective optimization model based on real-time pricing is represented to minimize the consumption and inconvenience costs in addition to environmental pollution [33]. In [34], an optimal simultaneous day-ahead scheduling and hourly reconfiguration framework in distribution systems considering responsive loads are developed. Four different categories of loads are considered as interruptible, adjustable, shiftable, and fixed load to enable demand-side participation in incentive-based programs combined with price-based programs. A two-stage planning method considering price-based DRP is proposed for multi-energy systems [35]. The upper stage is designed to minimize the capital and operation costs by deploying DERs. In the lower stage, the load patterns of shiftable customers are revised based on the nodal energy price calculated in the upper stage, thereby minimizing the consumption expenditure of customers by using an integrated DRP. In [36], an integrated planning model is developed to inspect an RER-based standalone MG's techno-economic sustainability. The proposed model develops a novel renewable generation-based dynamic pricing DR scheme for improving the overall system flexibility. A multi-objective optimization framework for the optimal design of an MG is introduced in [37]. The economics of scale as a function of DERs sizing is regarded in the model to boot. The model also establishes a DR model

based on a day-ahead real-time pricing mechanism to modify the daily load curve. The economic viability of an emission-neutral MCMG is assessed from economic, reliability, and environmental outlooks [38]. The model develops a novel real-time pricing mechanism to avoid the likelihood of any other peak occurrence, which is measured as the expense of generating one kilowatt-hour of energy given from different installed DGs. The authors in [39] propose an approach for MG operators to determine DR incentives for compensating customers' discomfort. The given incentive varies based on the participants' discomfort level and the load's economic value. A hierarchic optimization framework for MCMG expansion planning is proposed regarding the electricity transactions between adjacent MCMGs [40]. An economic model for the direct load control program is also developed to remotely shut down controllable loads on short notice during contingent conditions. A tri-level MG planning framework is introduced for determining distributed generations (DGs)' optimal capacity configuration and controllable loads [41]. The model's objective function embraces the installation cost of smart appliances and operation cost for trading control right of controllable loads from customers.

Table 1 presents the taxonomy of the reviewed papers in MG planning studies. It also places the paper at hand in context within the current literature. From the table, it is clear that the existing studies have overlooked the effect of demand-side smart appliances' cost on enabling the potential responsive customers and inspecting the techno-economic analysis of MCMG deployments profoundly. Besides, to enable demand-side flexibilities, investment-based incentives to smarten up power infrastructure by means of equipping customers with modern automation tools such as energy management systems and efficient information and communication technologies, which directly impact energy planning and savings, have been overlooked in the MCMG planning problems. Thus, this work aims to assess the techno-economic performance of a customer MCMG that provides power to a small industrial zone of 12 customers in Golpayegan, Iran. The model not only determines the optimal mix and size of DERs power/energy ratings within the MCMG but also identifies the ideal participation rate of potential responsive customers that are required to be equipped with smart appliances. The demand shifting or rescheduling program is merely employed as the most economical approach for establishing DR with no noticeable service impacts on customers, which not only contributes energy savings but also provides economic benefits for the customers. Herein, responsive customers are paid by shifting down (reward payments) and are penalized by shifting up (penalty payments) regarding the hourly energy demand shifting price. The model's objective is to minimize the total planning cost of the MCMG associated with DERs investment and replacement, DR enabling technology, loan payoff, operation, maintenance, peak demand charge, energy demand shifting reward or penalty, emission, and unserved energy, subject to given reliability and online reserve levels. Besides, the available budget impact on the optimal sizing and financial feasibility of MCMGs in various economic terms such as present-worth value, LCOE, discounted payback period, and profitability index is scrutinized. Besides, the model

incorporates the capital investment loan (CIL) as an incentive to enable users for active participation in DRPs via the installation of demand-side smart technologies. Two typical days of three typical seasons comprising summer, winter, and intermediate seasons are selected to represent the whole year and burden the complexity of computations. By and large, the proposed framework assists investors in deciding whether or not to invest in MCMG installation regarding economic, reliability, and environmental aspects. In the end, the planning problem is solved using the mixed-integer programming model of GAMS. The novel contribution of the proposed method, if compared to previous works are as follows:

- Proposing a comprehensive model that embraces technical, environmental, and reliability aspects for scrutinizing the financial feasibility of MCMG projects
- Associating participation rate of potential responsive customers as a variable to the installation of demand-side smart measurement and informing technologies
- Proposing a reward-penalty DRP as a function of real-time DR shifting tariffs for enabling potential responsive customers to mitigate peaks
- Investigating the effects of DR enabling technology investment-based incentives on the optimal sizing and financial feasibility of MCMGs
- Designing a small-scale multi-energy system including electricity, heat, natural gas, and hydrogen to enhance the energy efficiency and energy supply flexibility

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Sections 2 presents the model outline and formulation of the MCMG planning problem. Section 3 performs numerical simulations on a test MCMG system based on a real-life industrial park and discusses the results. The concluding remarks are provided in Section 4.

2 | MODEL OUTLINE AND FORMULATION

The MCMG is an advanced technology that provides economic benefits for its stakeholders. Smart grid technologies such as dispatchable and non-dispatchable distributed generations (DGs), storages, and DRPs can be indisputably integrated within MCMGs to provide salient complementary propositions to customers. The salient feature of MCMG is its islanding capability to ensure an uninterruptable supply of critical assets. The proposed model aims at minimizing the MCMG total planning cost (1) comprising the investment and replacement costs of DERs, DR enabling technology cost, loan payoff, operation and maintenance costs, energy demand shifting reward or penalty payment, peak demand charge, emission cost, and unserved energy cost.

$$OF = \sum_j \omega_j \cdot \left(\begin{array}{l} IC_j + RC_j + DC_j + LP_j + OC_j \\ +MC_j + SC_j + PC_j + EC_j + UC_j \end{array} \right) \quad (1)$$

TABLE 1 Literature review of various work on MG planning problems

Reference	DERs consideration for optimal sizing										Objective function terms										Economic metrics					Demand-side flexibility											
	Architecture	Energy carriers	CHP/Diesel/Micro turbine	FC	Boiler	EHP	PV	WT	ESS-Power	ESS-Energy	TSS-Power	TSS-Energy	HSS-Power	HSS-Energy	Investment cost	Replacement cost	DR enabling cost	Loan payment	Operation cost/benefit	Maintenance cost	Demand shifting cost/benefit	Peak demand charge	Emission cost/limit	Unsaved energy cost	Net present cost	Levelized cost of energy	Discounted payback period	Profitability index	Reliability	Online reserve	Battery degradation	Responsive customers	Investment-based incentive	Reward-Penalty incentive	DR ratio determination	Optimization method	
[5]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MINLP	
[6]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	PSO		
[7]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[9]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	PSO		
[10]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[12]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[14]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[15]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[16]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[17]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[18]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MIQCP		
[25]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	GA		
[26]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	HOMER		
[27]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	APSO		
[28]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MIQP		
[29]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[30, 31]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[32]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[36]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP		
[40]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	IAGA	
[41]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	PSO	
[44]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MFOA	
This Study	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP

MINLP, Mixed-integer nonlinear programming; PSO, Particle swarm optimization; MILP, Mixed-integer linear programming; MIQCP, Mixed-integer quadratically constrained programming; GA, Genetic algorithm; APSO, Accelerated PSO; MIQP, Mixed-integer quadratic programming; IAGA, Integrated Adaptive GA and MFOA, Moth-flame optimization algorithm.

*The MCMG is grid-connected but encounters outage in some periods of the year.

The investment cost of DERs (2) comprises the investment cost of DGs (derived by multiplying the DGs' capital cost times their installed power capacity), and the investment cost of storage systems associated with installed power and energy capacities (calculated by the storage systems' capital cost times their installed power/energy capacity). The replacement cost is calculated using (3), which denotes the capital replacement cost of DERs times their installed power/energy capacities. The concept of DR is executed by installing smart sensors, measurement devices, lighting control systems, two-way communications systems, and advanced energy management systems, which enables responsive users to respond to dynamic tariffs. The DR enabling technology cost (4) represents the cost of smart appliances' tools and efficient information and communication technologies for enabling the potential responsive customers and is defined herein as the DR enabling capital cost times the participation rate of enrolled responsive customers (DR intensity) as a function of peak power demand minus the CIL for demand-side technologies' installation. Herein, the planning solution determines how much of the demand-side technology cost would be covered by CIL. The annual loan payment (5) is measured by multiplying the CIL with the loan amortization value factor. The operation cost (6) denotes the cost or profit of exchanged power with the electric and natural gas utility companies. The maintenance cost of DGs is given in (7), which is calculated by the generated power of deployed units multiplied by their associated maintenance coefficients. The energy demand shifting cost (8) denotes the energy demand shifting up or down for the potential registered responsive customers multiplied by the energy demand shifting price. The net energy demand shifting could be either positive or negative, denoting the cost or profit for the potential customers. The peak demand charge is calculated in (9), which is interpreted as the peak demand price multiplied by the highest amount of purchased electricity from the power utility company during a billing period. Besides, the Max function in this equation is linearized. The emission cost for the utility grid and deployed DGs is calculated in (10). The load shedding cost (11), which represents the cost of unserved electrical and thermal energies, is defined as the amount of load curtailments multiplied by the value of lost loads. Here, Δb reflects the time step length of an hour.

$$IC_y = \sum_{u \in \{G, W\}} CC_u \cdot P_u^{\max} + \sum_{u \in S} (CP_u \cdot P_u^{\max} + CE_u \cdot E_u^{\max}) \quad \forall y = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$RC_y = \sum_{u \in \{G, W\}} CCr_u(r_{uy}) \cdot P_u^{\max} + \sum_{u \in S} (CPr_u(r_{uy}) \cdot P_u^{\max} + CER_u(r_{uy}) \cdot E_u^{\max}) \quad (3)$$

$$DC_y = CD \cdot LPF \cdot \max(D_{(y=N_y)sd}^e) - CIL \forall y = 1 \quad (4)$$

$$LP_y = CIL \cdot \xi \quad (5)$$

$$OC_y = \Delta b \cdot \sum_s \sum_d \mu_{sd} \cdot \sum_b \left(+P_{ysdb}^{Net,e} \cdot \pi_{yb}^{Net,e} + P_{ysdb}^{Net,g} \cdot \pi_y^{Net,g} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$MC_y = \Delta b \cdot \sum_s \sum_d \mu_{sd} \cdot \sum_b \sum_{u \in \{G, W\}} P_{uysdb} \cdot \alpha_u^{main} \quad (7)$$

$$SC_y = \Delta b \cdot \sum_s \sum_d \mu_{sd} \cdot \sum_b \pi_{yb}^{shifting} \cdot \left(D_{ysdb}^{shup,e} - D_{ysdb}^{shdo,e} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$PC_y = \sum_s \eta_s \cdot \pi^{peak} \cdot \max(P_{ysdb}^{Net,e,+}) \quad (9)$$

$$EC_y = \Delta b \cdot \sum_s \sum_d \mu_{sd} \cdot \sum_b \pi^{em} \cdot \left(P_{ysdb}^{Net,e} \cdot EF^{Net,e} + \sum_{u \in \{G, W\}} P_{uysdb} \cdot EF_u \right) \quad (10)$$

$$UC_y = \Delta b \cdot \sum_s \sum_d \mu_{sd} \cdot \sum_b P_{ysdb}^{ens,l} \cdot \pi^{ens,l} \quad \forall l \in \{e, t\} \quad (11)$$

Equations (12) and (13) denote the present-worth value and loan amortization value factors.

$$\omega_y = 1 / (1 + i)^{y-1} \quad (12)$$

$$\xi = i / (1 - (1 + i)^{-N_y}) \quad (13)$$

Equation (14) ensures the electrical demand balance in which the power generation by DERs, and the exchanged power with the utility company, plus the curtailed electricity demand are equal to the electrical demand regarding the demand shifting potential plus the energy consumed by the electric heat pump (EHP) and electrolyser units. Likewise, the thermal demand balance constraint of the system is represented by (15), where the produced thermal energy by DERs plus the curtailed thermal demand is greater than or equal to the thermal demand. The total natural gas consumption dedicated to the combined heat and power (CHP) and gas boiler units is declared as (16). The available hydrogen to be consumed by the fuel cell (FC) can be provided by the reactor-reformer system, hydrogen storage system (HSS), and electrolyser unit, as demonstrated in (17). It is presumed that the system uses municipal solid waste as an available energy resource that can be collected from residential, agricultural, and industrial zones. The hydrogen production amount of the reactor-reformer system is a function of the municipal solid waste quantity collected from the site.

$$\sum_{u \in \{G, W\}} P_{uysdb}^e \pm \sum_{u \in HSS} P_{uysdb}^{dcb/cb} + P_{ysdb}^{Net,e} + P_{ysdb}^{ens,e} = D_{ysdb}^e + D_{ysdb}^{shup,e} - D_{ysdb}^{shdo,e} + \sum_{u \in \{ehp, electro\}} PD_{uysdb}^e \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{u \in G} P_{uysdb}^t \pm \sum_{u \in HSS} P_{uysdb}^{dcb/cb} + P_{ysdb}^{ens,t} \geq D_{ysdb}^t \quad (15)$$

$$P_{ysdb}^{Net,g} = \sum_{u \in \{chp, boiler\}} v_{mysdb} \quad (16)$$

$$P_{ysdb}^{byd} = Pref_{mysdb}^{byd} \pm \sum_{u \in hss} P_{mysdb}^{dcb/ch} + \sum_{u \in electro} PD_{mysdb}^e \cdot \alpha_u^{ef} \quad (17)$$

The energy generation by units comprising gas-fired units, EHP, FC, PV, and WT is modelled respectively, as (18)–(21). It is noteworthy that the power generation of the PV unit (21) is modelled as a function of irradiation and air temperature [42]. Besides, the degradation of the PV unit's power output for Yingly panels is regarded in the model. Similarly, the power curve (22) is utilized to evaluate the power output of WT as a function of wind speed. The generated power by DGs is limited by installed capacities (23). A binary variable is defined in (23) to declare the on/off commitment state of dispatchable units.

$$P_{mysdb}^l = v_{mysdb} \cdot \alpha_u^{ef,l} \cdot A_u \quad \forall u \in \{chp, boiler\}, \forall l \in \{e, t\} \quad (18)$$

$$P_{mysdb}^t = PD_{mysdb}^e \cdot \alpha_{usb}^{ef} \cdot A_u \quad \forall u \in ehb \quad (19)$$

$$P_{mysdb}^l = P_{ysdb}^{byd} \cdot \alpha_u^{ef,l} \cdot A_u \quad \forall u \in fc, \forall l \in \{e, t\} \quad (20)$$

$$P_{mysdb} = \left(\frac{P_u^{\max} \cdot \alpha_{iy}^{ef} \cdot A_u \cdot \tilde{p}_{nb} \cdot \overline{G_s^{ing}}}{(1 + \kappa \cdot (T_c - \tilde{T}_{r_s}))} \right) / G^{stc} \quad \forall u \in pv \quad (21)$$

$$P_{mysdb} = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq \tilde{v}_s \leq v^{ci} \text{ or } \tilde{v}_s \geq v^{eo} \\ P_u^{\max} \cdot \alpha_u^{ef} \cdot A_u \cdot \tilde{p}_{nb} \cdot \frac{\tilde{v}_s^2 - v^{ci^2}}{v^{r^2} - v^{ci^2}} & v^{ci} \leq \tilde{v}_s \leq v^r \\ P_u^{\max} \cdot \alpha_u^{ef} \cdot A_u \cdot \tilde{p}_{nb} & v^r \leq \tilde{v}_s \leq v^{eo} \end{cases} \quad \forall u \in wt \quad (22)$$

$$0 \leq P_{mysdb} \leq P_u^{\max} \cdot V_{mysdb} \quad \forall u \in \{G, W\} \quad (23)$$

The energy storage constraints are reflected in (24)–(29). The hourly stored energy is calculated in (24) as the stored energy in the previous hour, energy loss, and the net charged/discharged power. Additionally, the storage net charge is presumed to be zero at the end of each day (25). The energy storage power in both charging and discharging modes is restricted by installed power rating (26). Constraint (27) limits the storage state of charge to prevent overcharging. Commonly, the electrical storage system (ESS) has a warranty on its throughput, which declares a specific amount of energy delivery throughout its lifetime. Constraints (28)–(29) restrict the amount of energy that cycles through the battery annually.

$$E_{mysdb} = \left(E_{mysdb(b-1)} - E_{mysdb} \cdot \alpha_u^{loss} \right) \cdot A_u \quad \forall u \in S \quad (24)$$

$$\sum_b (P_{mysdb}^{ch} - P_{mysdb}^{dcb} / \alpha_u^{ef}) \cdot \Delta b = 0 \quad \forall u \in S \quad (25)$$

$$0 \leq P_{mysdb}^{dcb/ch} \leq P_u^{\max} \quad \forall u \in S \quad (26)$$

$$E_u^{\max} \cdot (1 - DOD_u) \leq E_{mysdb} \leq E_u^{\max} \quad \forall u \in S \quad (27)$$

$$Thr_{iy}^{annual} = \sum_s \sum_d \mu_{sd} \cdot \sum_b \left((P_{mysdb}^{ch} + P_{mysdb}^{dcb} / \alpha_u^{ef}) \cdot \Delta b + E_{mysdb} \cdot \alpha_u^{loss} \right) \quad \forall u \in ess \quad (28)$$

$$Thr_{iy}^{annual} \leq E_u^{\max} \cdot Thr_u / EL_u \quad \forall u \in ess \quad (29)$$

The installed power and energy capacity of DERs should be within their allowable installation capacity (31). The binary variable I_u^{com} indicates the investment state of DERs.

$$\underline{P}_u^{cap} \cdot I_u^{inv} \leq P_u^{\max} \leq \overline{P}_u^{cap} \cdot I_u^{inv} \quad \forall u \in \{G, W, S\} \quad (30)$$

$$\underline{E}_u^{cap} \cdot I_u^{inv} \leq E_u^{\max} \leq \overline{E}_u^{cap} \cdot I_u^{inv} \quad \forall u \in S \quad (31)$$

In this paper, the shiftable load DR model of paper [38] is employed to enable the demand-side management, as formulated in (32)–(35). It is worth noting that the maximum hourly amount of demand shifting is constrained by the determined participation rate of enabled responsive customers. Herein, Equations (33) and (34) are linearized.

$$\sum_b D_{ysdb}^{sbup,e} = \sum_b D_{ysdb}^{sbd,e} \quad (32)$$

$$0 \leq D_{ysdb}^{sbup,e} \leq D_{ysdb}^e \cdot LPF \cdot IS_{ysdb}^{sbup,e} \quad (33)$$

$$0 \leq D_{ysdb}^{sbd,e} \leq D_{ysdb}^e \cdot LPF \cdot IS_{ysdb}^{sbd,e} \quad (34)$$

$$0 \leq IS_{ysdb}^{sbup,e} + IS_{ysdb}^{sbd,e} \leq 1 \quad (35)$$

Amounts of exchanged electricity and natural gas with the utility are constrained by the networks capacities in (36)–(37). Equation (36) is also modified by including a binary parameter that indicates the MCMG islanding state in case of any power outage events at the electric utility network.

$$\left| P_{ysdb}^{Net,e} \right| \leq \overline{P}^{Net,e} \cdot I_{ysdb}^{Net,e} \quad (36)$$

$$0 \leq P_{ysdb}^{Net,g} \leq \overline{P}^{Net,g} \quad (37)$$

The load shedding scheme is utilized to ensure the balance of power between the generation and consumption in the MCMG (38). The equivalent loss factor is utilized in this paper to assess

the reliability level of the MCMG (39). Equivalent loss factor criteria should be restricted annually (40), which is commonly considered below 0.01% for developed countries.

$$0 \leq P_{ysdb}^{ens,l} \leq (D_{ysdb}^l + D_{ysdb}^{sbup,l} - D_{ysdb}^{shda,l}) \quad \forall l \in \{e, t\} \quad (38)$$

$$ELF_y = \left(\sum_s \sum_d \mu_{sd} \cdot \sum_b P_{ysdb}^{ens,e} / D_{ysdb}^e \right) / \left(N_b \cdot \sum_s \sum_d \mu_{sd} \right) \quad (39)$$

$$ELF_y \leq \overline{ELF}_y \quad (40)$$

In order to ensure reliable operation of deployed MCMG, the online reserve constraint (41) is imposed to compensate for any sudden change either in generation or demand. Herein, the Min function is linearized to achieve the optimal solution. The required online reserve can be determined as a certain percentage of the critical load at each hour (42).

$$R_{ysdb} \leq \sum_{u \in \{chp, fc\}} (P_u^{\max} \cdot A_u - P_{ysdb}^e) + \sum_{u \in \{ess\}} \alpha_u^{ef} \cdot \min(E_{ysdb} / N_b \cdot \Delta b, P_u^{\max}) \quad (41)$$

$$R_{ysdb} = D_{ysdb}^e \cdot RM \quad (42)$$

The capital investment fund (CIF) on the project is limited (43), which accordingly affects the expansion planning project. The total investment cost of the MCMG project equates to the investment cost of DERs and DR enabling technologies.

$$TIC = IC_y + DC_y \leq CIF \quad \forall y = 1 \quad (43)$$

Governmental incentives and subsidies are available to encourage investment in demand-side smart measurement and informing appliances in order to enable customers' participation in DRPs. Persuading the MCMG investors to deploy demand-side smart technologies, the project can be financed by a long-term loan (44).

$$CIL \leq CD \cdot LPF \cdot \max(D_{(y=N_y)ysdb}^e) \quad \forall y = 1 \quad (44)$$

Apart from the terms above, the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) [43], discounted payback period and profitability indices considering savings (DPP and PI) [44], renewable energy and conventional power penetration metrics (REP and MCPP) [42] are measured in this paper.

3 | SIMULATIONS RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study deploys an MCMG test system based on a real-life industrial park (33°32'55.86" N, 50°18'02.12" E) in

FIGURE 1 Schematic diagram of the proposed MCMG

Golpayegan, Iran. The schematic representation of the proposed MCMG under deployment is presented in Figure 1. The characteristics of candidate DERs are given in Tables 2 and 3. Figure 2 shows the initial forecasted electrical and thermal load profiles of the industrial park for two typical days (weekdays and weekends) of three typical seasons representing summer, intermediate (spring/autumn), and winter seasons. The electricity and natural gas market prices are obtained from the online ISO-New England and Henry Hub Natural Gas data repositories. The power exchange of the MCMG with the electric utility grid is subject to a line capacity limit of 5 MW. The required parameters for the MCMG deployment are represented in Table 4. The average seasonal wind speed, solar irradiation, and air temperature of Golpayegan City are gathered from meteorology websites. The planning horizon is 25 years. Herein, we assume the DR enabling cost will be fully covered by a long-term loan (25 years) at a low-interest rate. Twenty-four hours of islanding per year is considered on average based on historical outages data obtained from the Golpayegan Electric Utility Company. The problem was formulated by mixed-integer programming and solved by GUROBI of GAMS 24.1. Three cases are studied as follows:

- Case 1: MCMG planning as a function of CIF
- Case 2: Impact of DR enabling capital cost on planning
- Case 3: Impact of investment-based incentives on the ratio of smartened customers for optimal MCMG planning

It is noteworthy to point out that the CILs as an incentive to encourage the installation of DR enabling technology appliances are disregarded in cases 1 and 2.

Case 1: MCMG planning is solved for a variety of CIFs. The optimal size and mix of deployed DERs with respect to CIF variations are depicted in Figure 3. The detailed DERs sizing are outlined in Appendix (Table A1). It is noteworthy that the

TABLE 2 Dispatchable and non-dispatchable units characteristics

Unit	Capital investment/ replacement costs (\$/kW)	Maintenance coefficient (\$/kWh)	Electrical/thermal efficiency (%)	Availability (%)	Lifetime (year)
CHP	300/300	0.01258	35/50	96	20
FC	1500/1500	0.00900	50/34	100	5
Boiler	45/45	0.00870	0/90	97	10
EHP	250/250	0.00300	97/0	98	15
PV	550/550	0.00310	–	96	25
WT	650/650	0.00600	90/0	96	25

TABLE 3 Energy storage characteristics

Unit	Capital investment/ replacement costs		Efficiency (%)	Loss efficiency (%)	Depth of discharge (%)	Availability (%)	Lifetime (year)
	Power (\$/kW)	Energy (\$/kWh)					
ESS	30/20	75/37	93	5	80	96	5
TSS	5/5	33/30	90	5	100	100	15
HSS	5/5	12/11	98	5	100	100	15

FIGURE 2 Average value of load forecasts in the initial year

energy ratings of storages are in kWh whereas the power ratings of storages, dispatchable and non-dispatchable units are in kW in the figure. It can be perceived from the results that the CHP would always be installed as the main and weightiest supplier of electrical and thermal demands. As shown, the size of CHP remains the same until the CIF gets less than \$2.78 mil-

lion, which then the planning solution initiates cutting the size moderately. Besides, the planning solution would install PV unit with a large capacity to fulfil a big part of the demand and sell the excess profitable electricity to the utility. Herein, the foremost reason for installing the PV unit rather than WT is merely originated from meteorological factors. The results also man-

TABLE 4 Required parameters for the MCMG planning

Discount rate (%)	5	Value of lost load (\$/kWh)	Electricity	3.65
Annual load growth rate (%)	2.9		Heat	0.107
Annual electricity price growth rate (%)	2.5	Emission factor (kg/kWh)	Utility	0.2556
Annual loan interest rate (%)	3.25		CHP	0.17606
Monthly demand charge (\$/kW)	6.192		Boiler	0.226
Required reserve margin (%)	10			
Equivalent loss factor (%)	0.01		FC	0.287
Demand response capital cost (\$/kW)	1200	CO ₂ e tax price (\$/kg.CO ₂ e)		0.0276

ifest that PV unit installation is extravagant in case the CHP unit with inadequate capacity is installed; thus, the size of the PV unit would fall dramatically by limiting the CIF. As shown, minute FC is sized and mounted for the available hydrogen resources produced by the municipal solid waste. Similarly, HSS utilization with adjusted power/energy rating is merely viable in the existence of sufficient municipal solid waste. When the CIF is between \$3.09 million and \$13.52 million, the planning solution would install thermal storage systems (TSS) in conjunction with heat suppliers as if its energy rating is 2.33 times the power rating for infinite CIF. However, by limiting the CIF progressively, the energy rating of TSS decreases monotonically since the energy and power ratings allocate sort of the same capacity, and then both power and energy ratings shrink bit by bit with almost identical ratings. Likewise, the ESS planning decision is almost similar to TSS, except that the planning solution would rather deploy a colossal amount of ESS in parallel with a small-scale CHP once the CIF gets extremely limited. It is worth noting that the ESS energy rating is calculated to be 2.86 times its power rating when the CIF gets less than \$1.33 million. Besides, either medium-sized EHP or boiler is interchangeably required to fulfil a share of thermal demand. Anyway, the EHP utilization is accentuated when the CIF is more extensive than \$5.82 million, whereas boiler installation is feasible for lower fund extents. Overall, dispatchable units would be preferably installed for every range of CIFs to ensure an uninterrupted supply of demands. The results highlight the eminence of governmental incentives together with regulations for persuading low-budget investors to deploy RERs.

Figure 4 illustrates the costs associated with MCMG planning as a function of CIF. The total cost varies by a constant-slope line with respect to the CIF. By decreasing the CIF from \$13.52 million to \$3.09 million, \$3.09 million to \$1.48 million, and \$1.48 million to \$0.87 million, the slopes of the total cost changes are calculated as 0.349, 11.132, and 90.87. Indisputably, the investment cost of units keeps dropping by limiting the CIF.

The same could be perceived for replacement cost, but, for all that, it suddenly ascends when the CIF gets less than \$1.2 million. The result also advocates that enabling responsive users is realizable only if the CIF is larger than \$10.95 million. Herein, enabled responsive users by participating in reward-based DR program not only gain roughly half of the financed DR enabling technology cost but also they contribute energy savings by shifting their demands to off-peaks. In sum, the results reveal that responsive customers in company with DERs would only be enabled as a last resort to cope with price fluctuations. Moreover, by decreasing the CIF from \$13.52 million to \$3.09 million, the accrued operational cash inflows decrease by about 5.2%, whereas the maintenance cost slightly increases by about 0.9%. Thereafter, an intense decrease is initiated in the operational cash inflows and ultimately depleted wholly when the CIF drops to \$2.03 million. Limiting the CIF progressively results in a remarkable increase in the operation cost from \$2.92 million to \$22.91 million. In contrast, the maintenance cost keeps dropping. According to the figure, decreasing the CIF from \$13.52 million to \$1.2 million would cause an increase followed by a steep decrease in the emission cost, but, after that, it abruptly goes up and down on the grounds of boiler removal. On the other hand, the peak demand charge remains unchanged until the CIF gets less than \$1.64 million, denoting the customers rather purchase electricity from the utility at any cost instead of curtailing demands. Besides, the load shedding cost for partially curtailing low-prioritized thermal demands increases from \$0.4 million to \$1.99 million by decreasing the CIF from \$13.52 million to \$1.83 million. The load shedding cost is rigorously worsened by inadequate sizing of CHP for CIF less than \$2.78 million. However, limiting the CIF more and more would cause an intense unserved cost such that it embraces a vast majority of the total planning cost, imposed by curtailing sensitive electrical loads. Overall, the economic feasibility of MCMG-based systems is verified for CIF beyond \$2.51 million since the accumulated revenue streams surpass the investment costs.

The results of economic metrics changes with respect to CIF variations are shown in Figure 5. Results show that by decreasing the CIF from \$13.52 million to \$0.87 million, distinct outcomes in terms of various economic measures are procured, for example, the discounted payback period would become shorter and shorter up until the CIF drops to \$1.08 million, on the contrary, LCOE would increase trivially followed by a drastic escalation which could turn the project into an unattractive case. Further, the project can be assessed from the profitability index outlook as if the higher it rates, the more profitable the project becomes. Nevertheless, LCOE within the range of \$0.00105/kWh–\$0.06381/kWh is realized for CIF larger than \$0.97 million, apart from the last scenario. Thus, the financial feasibility of the MCMG deployment is verified since the determined LCOEs are lower than the average retail rate of \$0.086/kWh. Lastly, the DR intensity of only the first three scenarios is settled to be 27%, 13%, and 1%, given that the DR capability merit of the proposed model would be merely justified for CIF larger than \$10.95 million. It is worth pointing out that load responsiveness would not be realized with-

FIGURE 3 Results of technologies optimum size as a function of CIF in Case 1

FIGURE 4 Cost breakdown of deployed MCMG as a function of CIF in Case 1

FIGURE 5 Effect of CIF variations on MCMG economic metrics in Case 1

FIGURE 6 Effect of changes in DR enabling cost on DR intensity in Case 2

out employing reward-penalty programs, even in the first three scenarios.

Case 2: The sensitivity of the planning solution concerning DR enabling capital cost is studied for a boundless CIF in this case. Figure 6 shows the results and illustrates that a decline in capital cost of DR enabling would increase the DR intensity within the MCMG. The change in DR intensity also has a direct impact on the optimal size and mixture of deployed DERs and consequently affects the planning cost. The overall installed capacity of units is reduced by 7.4% from 51.8 to

47.9 MW by the lower participation rate of responsive users; so that DR implementation significantly impacts the DER penetration level. The results advocate that more massive PV penetrations would be realized by a higher participation rate of responsive users, for example, a PV unit with full capacity is deployed by 100% DR intensity. On the other hand, a smaller amount of ESS would be deployed by a higher participation rate of customers. Similarly, the same solution nearly results in TSS installation, but with smaller changes in size. Besides, by the higher participation rate of customers, the size of CHP

FIGURE 7 Power penetration levels as a function of DR intensity in Case 2

and EHP decreases trivially, whereas the boiler’s size expands faintly.

The REP and MCPP trends with respect to DR intensity are presented to shed some light on the planning results to boot (see Figure 7). According to the results, the total planning cost would vary between \$2.91 million and \$3.28 million with respect to DR intensity (100–0%). In detail, the investment in DERs, particularly renewables, elevates by DR intensity of over 68.9%, which consequently leads to a significant reduction in emission and load shedding costs. By and large, the results advocate that the DR enabling technology cost is a decisive factor for enabling potential responsive customers within customer MCMGs.

Case 3: From a financial perspective, the capital cost of demand-side smart measurement and informing appliances is colossal, posing an extended return on investment on the MCMG project. The financial issue, however, will become less of a concern in the long run as the technological advances are causing considerable price drops in DR smart technologies. Nonetheless, the governments must apply a variety of policies and regulations, including both investment-based and reward-penalty incentives, to support investments in demand-side smart technologies in the short term. Thus, MCMG planning incorporating the investment-based and reward-penalty incentives on DR smart technologies is studied in this case to overcome the problem in previous cases.

The optimal ratio of smartened users within the MCMG in addition to the settled CILs in each scenario is illustrated in Figure 8. As shown, the DR intensity for the boundless budget would be 100%, but it is gradually decreasing by limiting the CIF and eventually ends up to 0% when the CIF drops to \$4.91 million. Herein, the determined DR intensity is directly dependent on the PV unit sizing as if the higher the PV unit proliferates, the wider demand-side flexibilities are needed to cope with

renewable fluctuations in addition to using the production more efficiently. However, when the CIF is between \$3.22 million and \$4.91 million, the planning solution even would not rather take out loans to smarten up power infrastructures because the DER local generation never exceeds or shortens the MCMG demand, and thereby the load responsiveness would not unlock any benefits to the MCMG investor. Nonetheless, decreasing the CIF more and more would cause a steep increase in DR intensity providing benefits from customers’ participation in DRPs and averting monthly peak demand charges, but, after that, it abruptly swings on the grounds of the changes in the boiler sizing and more importantly alleviating sensitive electrical load shedding during outages. It is also noteworthy to mention that heat producers’ sizing could be directly affected by the DR intensity determination when the budget is limited. Lastly, the utmost settled investment loan to cover the demand-side smart technologies’ cost is \$4.4 million, which resulted in 100% DR flexibilities.

The optimal size and mix of deployed DERs with respect to CIF variations along with settled CILs are illustrated in Figure 9. As can be seen, the DERs sizing trends as a function of CIF in case 3 are almost the same as case 1 except that the planning solution would not install ESS in parallel with CHP units once the budget gets extremely limited. Hereupon, the planning solution would rather install gas boilers to provide the heat demands and leverage demand-side flexibilities to manage the electrical demands in lieu of utilizing ESS when the CIF is limited. Besides, the size variation of deployed units in case 3 with respect to case 1 is depicted to provide delineated insights and a better understanding of the effect of investment-based incentives on the MCMG planning results (see Figure 10). As can be seen, when the CIF is larger than \$6.06 million, incorporating CILs as an incentive for enabling load responsiveness

FIGURE 8 The optimal ratio of smartened customers and settled CILs in each scenario of Case 3

FIGURE 9 Results of technologies optimum size as a function of CIF incorporating CIL in Case 3

would cause a moderate decrease in sizing of EHP unit and energy ratings of ESS and TSS units, whereas the size of gas boiler levels up relatively to provide the local heat demands. On the other hand, when the CIF of the project is between \$1.54 million and \$6.6 million, there are no sensible changes in the DERs sizing. Nonetheless, a dramatic change in the size of the boiler (upward) and ESS power and energy ratings (down-

ward) is realized for CIF below \$1.39 million. On the whole, the results underscore the importance of DR enabling technology investment-based incentives on the DER technology mix.

Financial breakdowns of the associated costs in case 3 are represented in Figure 11. As can be seen, the MCMG total cost initiates decreasing relatively slightly by limiting the CIF up until the CIF drops to \$3.22 million which then it starts

FIGURE 10 The DERs sizing deviation of Case 3 compared to Case 1

FIGURE 11 Cost breakdown of deployed MCMG as a function of CIF incorporating CIL in Case 3

rising precipitously due to an intense increase in the operation cost, peak demand charge, unserved energy cost, and loan payment for DR enabling technologies. Herein, the loan payments are lower than the received CIL because the accumulated loan payments over the planning horizon are transferred to the first year using the present-worth value factor. The load responsiveness would cause the system's total cost to fall within the range of \$2.90 million–\$40.89 million, resulting in around 11%–50% reduction in case 3 compared to case 1, respecting the available CIF. Thus, financial incentives on DR enabling technologies strongly affect the economic feasibility and the optimal design of the MCMG project. Moreover, the minimum, average, and maximum LCOE of the deployed MCMGs in case 3 are \$0.00095/kWh, \$0.0076/kWh, and \$0.0297/kWh, which are 9%, 45%, and 78% less than the results from case 1. By and large, investment-based incentives on demand-side smart appliances would effectively lower CIFs, highlighting the role incentives could play in cultivating the economic viability of MCMGs equipped with smart demand-side technologies.

We also investigate whether the planning solutions would still install smart power infrastructures to enable load responsiveness without employing reward-penalty programs. Herein, the investment-based loans are available for the MCMG investor. The results manifest that the load responsiveness without utilizing reward-penalty programs is realizable only when the budget gets extremely limited (less than \$1.51 million), resulting in hefty peak demand charges and operation costs. Thus, enabling DR features incorporating only investment-based incentives would be economic for limited budget extents so as to contribute energy savings by shifting the demands from peaks to off-peaks. By and large, the minimum, average, and maximum LCOE of the deployed MCMGs for different budget extents are \$0.0011/kWh, \$0.0081/kWh, and \$0.0314/kWh, respectively.

Taken together, the findings have led us to conclude that governmental investment-based incentives on demand-side smart appliances in addition to reward-penalty programs are prerequisite for enabling customers to dynamically participate in DRPs, leaving aside the annual relatively low-cost reduction of intelligent technologies. Thus, the results aid and inform policymakers in drafting regulations for facilitating the successful implementation and deployment of MCMGs equipped with intelligent measurement and informing appliances.

4 | CONCLUSION

A planning framework for customer multi-carrier microgrids considering technical, economic, and reliability criteria was proposed. The optimal configuration mix of distributed energy resources, along with the ideal ratio of potential responsive customers, was determined within the proposed multi-carrier microgrid while minimizing the total planning cost incorporating both investment-based and reward-penalty incentives to enable load responsiveness. Indeed, this study investigated the impact of demand response enabling incentives on an industrial multi-carrier microgrid's optimal sizing and financial feasibility. Numerical simulations were presented to investigate

the impact of the capital investment fund and smart appliances cost incorporating incentives on the planning solutions. It was certified that responsive users in parallel with distributed energy resources would only be enabled as a last resort to tackle price fluctuations without incorporating investment-based incentives. Thus, an intense drop in capital cost of demand-side smart appliances' tools is vital for motivating customers to install advanced measuring and informing technologies, and consequently enabling users to participate in demand response programs, which will be realized in the long run with the advancement in intelligent technologies. Until then, the government or the utility should launch incentive programs to encourage users to invest in demand-side smart technologies to exploit flexibility services from elastic and smartened users. The results advocated that incorporating both investment-based and reward-penalty incentives caused the planning solution to smarten up power infrastructures at almost all budget extents. Besides, load responsiveness incorporating only investment-based incentives was found to be realizable and cost-effective for limited budget extents so as to reduce the load curtailment and contribute energy savings. It was also shown that the higher participation rate of responsive users would proliferate renewable penetrations, underlining the eminence of load responsiveness. It was verified that incorporating both investment-based and reward-penalty incentives could indisputably reduce the system's cost by about 11%–50%, respecting the available budget. All in all, the economic viability of the multi-carrier microgrid incorporating capital investment loans as incentives was examined and verified in various economic terms to help financiers in deciding whether or not to invest in multi-carrier microgrid installations equipped with smart demand-side technologies.

A follow-on work of this research will focus on studying the impact of investment-based and production-based incentives on renewable energy resources, batteries, and demand-side enabling technologies on the optimal design and economic viability of the MCMG projects.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data are available with the first author upon request.

NOMENCLATURE

Indices

<i>boiler</i>	Index for gas boiler unit
<i>cbp</i>	Index for combined heat and power unit
<i>d</i>	Index for days
<i>ebp</i>	Index for electric heat pump unit
<i>electro</i>	Index for electrolyser unit
<i>ess</i>	Index for electrical storage system
<i>fc</i>	Index for fuel cell unit
<i>h</i>	Index for hours
<i>hss</i>	Index for hydrogen storage system
<i>l</i>	Index for carrier comprising {e: electricity, t: heat}
<i>pv</i>	Index for photovoltaic unit
<i>s</i>	Index for seasons

ts	Index for thermal storage system
u	Index for distributed energy resources
wt	Index for wind turbine unit
y	Index for years

Sets

G	Set of dispatchable units
S	Set of storage system units
W	Set of nondispatchable units (wind and solar)

Parameters

A	Availability coefficient of units
CC	Capital cost of distributed generations (\$/kW)
$CCr(r)$	Capital replacement cost of distributed generations (\$/kW)
CD	Capital cost of demand response assets (\$/kW)
CE/CP	Capital cost of storages – energy/power (\$/kW and \$/kWh)
$CEr(r)$	Capital replacement cost of storages – energy (\$/kWh)
CIF	Capital investment fund of the project (\$)
$CP(r)$	Capital replacement cost of storages – power (\$/kW)
D^l	Load demand for carrier l (kW)
DOD	Depth of discharge of storages (%)
E^{cap}/P^{cap}	Installation energy/power capacity of units (kWh and kW)
EF	CO ₂ e emission conversion factor (kg/kWh)
EL	The economic lifetime of units (years)
ELF	Maximum equivalent loss factor (pu)
G^{ing}	Solar irradiation forecast (W/m ²)
G^{stc}	Solar irradiation in standard condition (1000 W/m ²)
i	Discount rate (%)
$I^{Net,e}$	Binary islanding parameter (1 if grid-connected, 0 if islanded)
N	Total number
$P^{Net,e/g}$	Flow limit between the microgrid and network (kW)
pp	Normalized generation forecast of renewables
R	Available online reserve of the microgrid (kW/h)
RM	Required online reserve percentage (%)
T_c, T_r	Cell and forecast air temperatures (°C)
Thr	Storage throughput (kWh/kWh)
v	Wind speed forecast (m/s)
$v^{ci/co/r}$	Cut-in, cut-out, rated speed of wind turbine (m/s)
α^{ef}	Efficiency of units (%)
α^{loss}	Energy loss coefficient of storages
α^{main}	Maintenance coefficient of units (\$/kWh)
π^{em}	CO ₂ e tax price (\$/kg.CO ₂ e)
π^{ens}	Value of lost load (\$/kWh)
$\pi^{Net,e}$	Electricity purchase/sale price (\$/kWh)
$\pi^{Net,g}$	Natural gas price (\$/kWh)
π^{peak}	Peak demand price (\$/kW.month)
$\pi^{shifting}$	Energy demand shifting price (\$/kWh)
κ	Maximum power temperature coefficient
μ/η	Number of days/months per season

ω	Present-worth value factor
ξ	Loan amortization value factor

Variables

CIL	Capital investment loan (\$)
$D^{shup/shdo}$	Shifted up/down electricity demand (kW)
DC	Microgrid demand response enabling cost (\$)
E	The stored energy of storages (kWh)
E^{max}	Installed energy capacity of storages (kWh)
EC	Microgrid emission cost (\$)
ELF	Equivalent loss factor (pu)
I^{inv}	Investment state of units (1 if installed, 0 otherwise)
IC	Microgrid investment cost of units (\$)
$IS^{shup/shdo}$	Shifting up/down binary indicator
LP	Microgrid loan payment (\$/y)
LPF	Demand response intensity rate (0–1)
MC	Microgrid maintenance cost (\$)
OC	Microgrid operation cost/profit (\$)
OF	Objective function (\$)
P	Output power of distributed generations (kW)
$p^{dch/ch}$	Energy storage discharging/charging power (kW)
$p^{ens,l}$	Load curtailment for carriers $l \in \{e, g\}$ (kW)
p^{hyd}	Available hydrogen (kWh)
p^{max}	Installed power capacity of units (kW)
$p^{Net,e/g}$	Exchanged power/gas with the utility company (kW)
$Pre^{f^{hyd}}$	Anaerobic reactor-reformer system output
PC	Microgrid peak demand cost (\$)
PD	Input electric energy of units comprising {electric heat pump and electrolyser} (kW)
RC	Microgrid replacement cost of units (\$)
SC	Microgrid energy demand shifting reward or penalty payment (\$)
Thr^{annual}	The annual amount of storage throughput (kWh/year)
TIC	Total investment cost of the project (\$)
UC	Microgrid unserved energy cost (\$)
V	Commitment state of dispatchable units (1 if on, 0 if off)
v	Natural gas consumption by gas-fired units (kW)

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How to cite this article: Azimian, M., Amir, V., Javadi, S., Siano, P., Alhelou, H.H.: Enabling demand response for optimal deployment of multi-carrier microgrids incorporating incentives. *IET Renew. Power Gener.* 16, 547–564 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1049/rpg2.12360>

APPENDIX

Table A1 presents the detailed DERs sizing as a function of CIF variations in case 1.

TABLE A1 Detailed DERs sizing as a function of CIF variations in case study 1

Scenario	CIF	CHP (MW)	Boiler (MW)	EHP (MW)	FC (MW)	PV (MW)	WT (MW)	ESS- power (MW)	TSS- power (MW)	HSS- power (MW)	ESS- energy (MWh)	TSS- energy (MWh)	HSS- energy (MWh)
{1 Orig.}	13.52	10.37	0.09	2.18	0.01	13.89	0.00	4.44	3.11	0.01	8.49	7.24	0.05
{2}	12.17	10.39	0.05	2.13	0.01	12.74	0.00	4.10	3.15	0.01	7.83	5.85	0.05
{3}	10.95	10.42	0.00	2.04	0.01	11.68	0.00	3.78	2.88	0.01	7.24	5.08	0.05
{4}	9.86	10.42	0.00	1.90	0.01	10.14	0.00	3.03	2.79	0.01	5.71	3.98	0.05
{5}	8.87	10.40	0.03	1.76	0.01	8.68	0.00	2.32	3.15	0.01	4.24	3.50	0.05
{6}	7.98	10.38	0.06	1.55	0.01	7.38	0.00	1.70	3.17	0.01	2.97	3.52	0.05
{7}	7.19	10.38	0.06	1.32	0.01	6.20	0.00	1.15	3.20	0.01	1.84	3.71	0.05
{8}	6.47	10.38	0.07	1.13	0.01	5.16	0.00	0.65	3.20	0.01	0.84	3.55	0.05
{9}	5.82	10.34	1.77	0.14	0.01	4.36	0.00	0.51	3.08	0.01	0.61	3.42	0.05
{10}	5.24	10.34	1.72	0.00	0.01	3.47	0.00	0.09	3.05	0.00	0.10	3.39	0.00
{11}	4.71	10.25	1.32	0.00	0.01	2.67	0.00	0.00	2.25	0.00	0.00	2.50	0.00
{12}	4.24	10.30	0.97	0.00	0.01	1.84	0.00	0.00	1.94	0.00	0.00	2.15	0.00
{13}	3.82	10.37	0.70	0.00	0.01	1.08	0.00	0.00	1.70	0.00	0.00	1.89	0.00
{14}	3.44	10.42	0.49	0.00	0.01	0.40	0.00	0.00	1.36	0.00	0.00	1.51	0.00
{15}	3.09	10.18	0.42	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.00
{16}	2.78	9.15	0.84	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
{17}	2.51	8.10	1.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
{18}	2.25	7.16	2.41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
{19}	2.03	6.30	3.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
{20}	1.83	5.53	3.70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
{21}	1.64	4.85	4.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
{22}	1.48	4.46	3.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
{23}	1.33	4.18	0.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.56	0.00	0.00
{24}	1.20	3.10	0.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.95	0.00	0.00	2.73	0.00	0.00
{25}	1.08	1.96	1.38	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.75	0.00	0.00	5.01	0.00	0.00
{26}	0.97	0.94	1.91	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.47	0.00	0.00	7.06	0.00	0.00
{27}	0.87	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.55	0.00	0.00	7.29	0.00	0.00